

Technical Marvels (2): Lebombo and Ishango bones

This series presents selected technical marvels from the fields of computing technology, mathematics, astronomy, surveying, time measurement, looms and automatons (automaton figures, chess-playing machines, musical automatons, automaton writers, drawing automatons, automaton clocks, picture clocks, globes, historical robots). The examples are largely from the 15th to 20th centuries and do not claim to be exhaustive. In particular, artifacts are included for which high-quality illustrations are available. Most of the objects come from Europe, with a few from Africa, America, Asia, and Australia. The order is predominantly chronological. Famous names such as Archimedes, Hipparchus, Heron of Alexandria, Leonardo da Vinci, Galileo Galilei, John Napier, Jost Bürgi, Blaise Pascal, Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz and Charles Babbage are associated with these works. In some cases, however, the inventors are unknown (e.g. abacus, Antikythera Mechanism, yupana, quipu), see [Technical Marvels – Communications of the ACM](#)

BY HERBERT BRUDERER

The earliest mathematical instruments include the Lebombo bone (around 40,000 BC, South Africa, see Figs. 1–4) and the Ishango bone (20,000 BC, Congo, see Fig. 5).

The following summary is taken from Francesco d’Errico, Lucinda Backwell, Paola Villa, Ilaria Degano, Jeannette J. Lucejko, Marion K. Bamford, Thomas F. G. Higham, Maria Perla Colombini, and Peter B. Beaumont: Early evidence of San material culture represented by organic artifacts from Border Cave, South Africa, published in: PNAS, August 14, 2012, volume 109, no. 33, page 13214:

„Recent archaeological discoveries have revealed that pigment use, beads, engravings, and sophisticated stone and bone tools were already present in southern Africa 75,000 y ago. Many of these artifacts disappeared by 60,000 y ago, suggesting that modern behavior appeared in the past and was subsequently lost before becoming firmly established. Most archaeologists think that San hunter–gatherer cultural adaptation emerged 20,000 y ago. However, reanalysis of organic artifacts from Border Cave, South Africa, shows that the Early Later Stone Age inhabitants of this cave used notched bones for notational purposes, wooden digging sticks, bone awls, and bone points similar to those used by San as arrowheads. A point is decorated with a spiral groove filled with red ochre, which closely parallels similar marks that San make to identify their arrowheads when hunting. A mixture of beeswax, Euphorbia resin, and possibly egg, wrapped in vegetal fibers, dated to ~40,000 BP, may have been used for hafting. Ornaments include marine shell beads and ostrich eggshell beads, directly dated to ~42,000 BP. A digging stick, dated to ~39,000 BP, is made of *Flueggea virosa*. A wooden poison applicator, dated to ~24,000 BP, retains residues with ricinoleic acid, derived from poisonous castor beans. Reappraisal of radiocarbon age estimates through Bayesian modeling, and the identification of key elements of San material culture at Border Cave, places the emergence of modern hunter–gatherer adaptation, as we know it, to ~44,000 y ago.“

Fig. 1: Notched bone from Border Cave, Lebombo Mountains (1), © Robert Hart, The McGregor Museum, Kimberley, South Africa

Fig. 2: Notched bone from Border Cave, Lebombo Mountains (2), © Robert Hart, The McGregor Museum, Kimberley, South Africa

Fig. 3: Notched bone from Border Cave, Lebombo Mountains (3), © Robert Hart, The McGregor Museum, Kimberley, South Africa

Fig. 4: Notched bone from Border Cave, Lebombo Mountains (4), © Robert Hart, The McGregor Museum, Kimberley, South Africa

Fig. 5. The Ishango bone (viewed from four sides). The 10 cm long, 20,000-year-old bone was found in 1950 during excavations along the Congolese bank of Lake Edward. A sharp piece of quartz is affixed to one end (at the top). The bone is of mammalian origin. The grip of the tool exhibits 168 parallel notches in all, engraved on three sides, arranged in groups © Institut royal des Sciences naturelles de Belgique, Brussels).

Note: To this day the meaning of the notches is not clear, although several explanations have been attempted (see *Have you heard of Ishango?*, Association pour la diffusion de l'information archéologique, Royal Belgian institute of natural sciences, Brussels, year not given, 21 pages).

Acknowledgments

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References

Francesco d'Errico, Lucinda Backwell, Paola Villa, Ilaria Degano, Jeannette J. Lucejko, Marion K. Bamford, Thomas F. G. Higham, Maria Perla Colombini, and Peter B. Beaumont: Early evi-

dence of San material culture represented by organic artifacts from Border Cave, South Africa, in: PNAS, August 14, 2012, volume 109, no. 33, pages 13214–13219

Francesco d’Errico, Lucinda Backwell, Paola Villa, Ilaria Degano, Jeannette J. Lucejko, Marion K. Bamford, Thomas F.G. Higham, Maria Perla Colombini, Peter P. Beaumont: Early Evidence of San material culture represented by Organic Artifacts from Border Cave, South Africa. Supporting Information Appendix. Archaeological context. Results. Materials and Methods. References, 52 pages

Meilensteine der Rechentechnik, De Gruyter, 3. Auflage 2020

Milestones in Analog and Digital Computing, Springer, 3rd edition 2020

Bruderer, Herbert: Meilensteine der Rechentechnik, De Gruyter Oldenbourg, Berlin/Boston, 3. Auflage 2020, Band 1, 970 Seiten, 577 Abbildungen, 114 Tabellen, <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110669664>

Bruderer, Herbert: Meilensteine der Rechentechnik, De Gruyter Oldenbourg, Berlin/Boston, 3. Auflage 2020, Band 2, 1055 Seiten, 138 Abbildungen, 37 Tabellen, <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110669671>

Bruderer, Herbert: Milestones in Analog and Digital Computing, Springer Nature Switzerland AG, Cham, 3rd edition 2020, 2 volumes, 2113 pages, 715 illustrations, 151 tables, translated from the German by Dr John McMinn, <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-40974-6>

Forthcoming

Bruderer, Herbert: Wendepunkte in der analogen und digitalen Welt, De Gruyter Oldenbourg, Berlin, Boston 2025, etwa 400 Seiten, 533 Abbildungen, 34 Tabellen

Bruderer, Herbert: Turning Points in the Analog and Digital World, ACM Book, New York, 2025, around 400 pages, 533 illustrations, 34 tables

Herbert Bruderer
Seehaldenstraße 26
Postfach 47
CH-9401 Rorschach
Switzerland
+41 71 855 77 11
herbert.bruderer@bluewin.ch
bruderer@retired.ethz.ch

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